

EC Seventh ERA-NET Project **EUPHRESCO 2**
(**EU**ropean **PHY**tosnaitary **RE**search **CO**ordination)

Deliverable 4.2

Website as a Platform 1

Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs | <https://secure.fera.defra.gov.uk/euphresco/public/calls/index.htm>

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The EUPHRESO Network website is now available at www.euphresco.net.

CALLS

- Research initiation round 2013**
Timetable
Table of (suggested) research topics
- Expression of interest for the UK-Dutch "Plant Health Research Fellowship Scheme"**
Applicants' Guide including the call specification and the Expression of Interest Form
- Expression of interest for the UK-Danish call on "Diagnostics and risk management for plant health threats in wood chips and bark for bio-energy imported from other continents"**
Applicants' Guide including the call specification and the Expression of Interest Form
- Research initiation round 2012**
Timetable
Table of (suggested) research topics
- Dropped topics**
View all dropped topics from current and previous research rounds
- Archive**
EUPHRESO Pilot Calls for Phytosanitary Research 2008

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RESEARCH PROJECTS

Title	Status	Report
VP1 - Detection and epidemiology of Poasphiviroids (DEP)	completed	Download
VP1 - Strategies for Ambrosia artemisiifolia control (AMBROSIA)	completed	Download
Diagnostic tools for the detection of fire blight, Erwinia amylovora (ERWINDECT)	completed	Download
VP1 - Phytosanitary efficacy of kiln drying (PEKID)	completed	Download
VP1 - Evaluating the risk of spread of Scapholectus litanus with propagation material (PROPSCAPH)	completed	Download
RP1 - Decision support systems for control of alien invasive macrophytes (DeCLAIM)	completed	Not yet available
RP1 - Development of validated procedures for whole genome amplification of DNA/RNA for quarantine plant pathogens and pests (Q-AMP)	completed	Not yet available
NCM1 - Ring testing of diagnostic methods for the identification of potato cyst nematodes and assessing resistance of potato cultivars	completed	Download
NCM1 - Ring test on diagnostic methods for Pantoea stewartii ssp. stewartii, maize bacterial blight	completed	Not yet available
NCM1 - Interlaboratory tests for the detection of Clavibacter michiganensis ssp. sepedonicus (potato ring rot) and Ralstonia solanacearum (potato brown rot)	completed	Not yet available
NCM1 - Validation of diagnostic methods for the detection and identification of widely-transmitted viruses of regulatory or quarantine concern to the EU	completed	Download
NCM2 - Development and validation of diagnostic methods for Gibberella circinata (Fusarium circinatum) cause of pitch pine canker	completed	Not yet available
NCM2 - Anoplophora longhorn beetle detection and risk management	completed	Not yet available
NCM2 - Detection and management of the quarantine nematodes Meloidogyne chitwoodi and Meloidogyne fallax	completed	Not yet available
NCM2 - Phylogenetic identification of quarantine bacterial plant pathogens	completed	Not yet available
NCM2 - Interlaboratory comparison and validation of detection methods for phytoplasmas of phytosanitary concern in European orchards	completed	Download
NCM2 - Development of pathotype-specific PCR tests for the identification of Synchytrium endobioticum pathotype 1 (D1)	completed	Not yet available

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